

MODELLING AN IMPROVED NOL RING TEST USING A REDUCED VOLUME METHOD FOR THE CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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Motivation

- The hoop ply hold most of the load
- The strength of CPV could be characterised by a part of a cylinder

- Less manufacturing and gripping issues to original NOL Ring tensile test -

Methodology

- The number of elements can be reduced based on the evaluation of the reduced volume method -

Comparison Study

- The Multiscale model applied only on the red region -

- The rest was modelled with linear elastic properties -

Cases	Fibre Vf (%)	Sectional Area (mm ²)	Cases	Fibre Vf (%)	Sectional Area (mm ²)
1	35	30	3	55	30
2		40	4		40

Conclusions

- Case 3 produced the most favourable comparison
- Via the reduced volume method, the strength of large composite structures can be evaluated
- The multiscale model can show the time dependent effect

References

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